

Chalcone Derivatives for Biological Potentials: A Strategy of Molecular Hybridization for Drug Design

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Review Article ABSTRACT

Keywords
Chalcone;
Molecular
hybridization;
Biological
potentials.

Article History
Accepted
March 2, 2022
Published
online
March 24, 2022

Naturally and synthetically derived hybrid molecules are promising sources for new drug development due to their multiple modes of action and other advantages. Chalcone, two important classes of synthetic chemistry affording diverse pharmacological activities, make themselves ideal blocks for building a chalcone hybrid scaffold as a bioactive agent. Provoked by the promising medicinal applications of such hybrids, the scientific community has reported dozens of chalcone hybrids with a wide spectrum of biological properties including anticancer, antimicrobial, antimalarial, antioxidant, antianxiety and so on, through synthetic hybridization strategy. It is expected to assist medicinal chemists in the effective and successful development of chalcone hybrids. In view of these observations, we herein report the literature review of Chalcone hybrids which possessing antimicrobial, antioxidant and antianxiety potential.

Graphical Abstract

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Introduction

Chalcone is one of the privileged medicinal pharmacophores, which appears is an important structural component in natural compounds and has generated great attention because of its interesting biological activity including antimicrobial action. Chromene constitutes the basic backbone of various types of polyphenols and is widely found in natural alkaloids, tocopherols, flavonoids, and anthocyanins. It is known that certain natural and synthetic chalcone derivatives possess important biological activities (Ahmad *et al.*, 2016). Chalcone is an aromatic ketone and an enone that forms the central core for a variety of important biological compounds, which are known collectively as chalcones or chalconoids. Chalcones can be prepared by an aldol condensation between benzaldehyde and acetophenone in the presence of sodium hydroxide as a catalyst. Chalcones are active lead molecules in medicinal chemistry for the discovery of new drugs. Chalcones have been reported to possess many useful biological properties including antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and anticancer and antioxidant activities (Nicolaou *et al.*, 2000; Rajindra *et al.*, 2008; Kotra *et al.*, 2010; Lahsasni *et al.*, 2014; Sökmen *et al.*, 2016). In view of these biological significances of coumarin and chalcones, a strategy of synthetic molecular hybridization between coumarins with chalcones is used to design number of coumarin-chalcone hybrids for therapeutic potentials (Khafagy *et al.*, 2002; Suresh *et al.*, 2010; Chetan *et al.*, 2017; Ren *et al.*, 2011).

Chalcone hybrids

Chavan *et al.*, (2016) reported synthesis in the medicinal significance of chalcones derivatives. These compounds they have backbone of the chalcones it has been reported in to the possess of various biological activities such as

antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, analgesic, antiplatelet, antiulcerative, antimalarial, anticancer, antiviral, antileishmanial, antioxidant, antitubercular, antihyperglycemic, immunomodulators, and function of the chalcones is responsible for the antimicrobial activity.

3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetraazolidinone

Elavarasan *et al.*, (2018) reported synthesis of the new chalcones by Claisen Schmidt condensation of the substituted benzaldehydes with 4-aminoacetanilide in the presence of base catalyst. These are responsible for the antimicrobial activity and compared with the standard drugs

N-(4-aminophenyl)cinnamamide

Jaiswal *et al.*, (2018) reported synthesis of chalcone and their heterocyclic analogue. Various structural modifications of the heterocyclic analogies chalcones synthesized have been made to explore its promising biological potential in the recent years. The various pharmacological activities of antihypertensive, antifungal, anticancer, anti-filarial, anti-protozoal, anti-HIV, antimalarial,

antioxidant, antiviral, antifungal, anticonvulsant, antibacterial.

(2E)-1-(1H-benzimidazol-2-yl)-3-(3,4,5-trimethoxyphenyl) prop-2-en-1-one

Ahmed *et al.*, (2016) reported Synthesis and anti-bacterial evaluation of new chalcone derivatives conjugates as possible mutual prodrug.

7-fluoro-2-methyl-6-(4-methylpiperazin-1-yl)-10-oxo-4-oxa-1-azatricyclo trideca-7,9(13)-diene-11-carboperoxoyl chloride

Sahoo *et al.*, (2017) reported synthesis of pyrimidines derivatives through Chalcones and its evaluation of their anthelmintic activity. In the present study, we focused in the environment-friendly processes used for the preparation of pyrimidine derivatives with pharmacological properties of antimicrobial.

4-(4-hydroxy-phenyl)-6-phenyl-pyrimidin-2(1H)-one (4e)

Jung *et al.*, (2017) reported synthesis of chalcone derivatives and their biological activities of molecular modelling studies to investigate of the chemical structural it characteristics for the biological activities of antibacterial, antimicrobial, and anti-neurotoxicity.

(2E,2'E)-1,1'-(5-(E)-3-(3-hydroxy-4-methoxyphenyl)acryloyl)-1,3-phenylenebis(3-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl)prop-2-en-1-one)

Kumar *et al.*, (2017) reported synthesis of some new schiff bases of pharmaceutical interest a series of schiff bases of diphenylamine derivatives have been synthesized and evaluated for the antibacterial activity.

2-(4-(1-(2,3-Dimethylphenylimino) methyl) phenoxy)N,N diphenylacetamide

Gaonkar *et al.*, (2017) reported synthesis and pharmacological properties of some chalcones. These chalcone derivatives is important for the antimicrobial, antifungal, anti mycobacterium, ant malarial, antiviral, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, antileishmanial anti-tumour, and anticancer properties.

hydroxy-nitrochalcone

Suwito *et al.*, (2014) reported a review on (E)-1-(4-aminophenyl)-3-(4-methoxyphenyl) prop-2-en-1-one, (E)-1-(4-aminophenyl)-3-(2,4-dimethoxyphenyl)prop-2-en-1-one, and (E)-1-(4-aminophenyl)-3-(2,3-dimethoxyphenyl)prop-2-en-1-one, these are produced the antimicrobial activity.

(E)-1-(4-aminophenyl)-3-(4-methoxyphenyl)prop-2-en-1-one

Chandrabose *et al.*, (2014) reported synthesis of the some new chalcones derivative Chalcones are naturally occurring compounds exhibiting broad spectrum biological activities including anticancer activity through multiple mechanisms.

(4-tetrahydropyrrolylcarbonyl-2,5-dimethoxychalcone)

Yerragunta *et al.*, (2013) reported a review on chalcones and its importance and they can also be synthesized in the laboratory these chalcones possess of a broad spectrum of biological activity including ant oxidative, antibacterial, anthelmintic, amoebicidal, antiulcer ,antiviral, insecticidal, antiprotozoal, anticancer, cytotoxicity and immunosuppressive.

5-methoxy-2-methyl-6-(3-phenylbut-3-en-1-yl)-4a,8a-dihydro-4H-chromen-4-one

Acknowledgments

The authors extend their gratitude to the Hon'ble Vice Chancellor and Dean, School of Pharmaceutical Sciences, IFTM University, Moradabad.

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